

AUTOMATED MEASUREMENT OF AIRCRAFT-LEVEL ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE

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ABSTRACT

Traditional Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) testing of aircraft for interference with onboard radio communications involves arbitrarily selecting 10 to 100 channels and listening for interference on the headset. Given that there are approximately 13,000 possible radio channels in the combined HF, VHF, and UHF ranges, industry is certifying the aircraft electronic systems as being compatible after testing less than one percent (1%) of the available channels. Choosing a maximum of 100 channels leaves large frequency gaps where interference may actually be occurring. Additionally, interference which does not break squelch may go undetected, but it can still cause a significant degradation of the operational range of the radio. If interference is detected, its actual magnitude cannot be accurately determined simply by listening or measuring the audio level present due to the Automatic Gain Control (AGC) action of the radio.

A refined method of testing for EMC involves applying newly automated test capabilities to this problem. These capabilities allow continuous sweeping across all frequency bands at sensitivities below -120 dBm in a timely manner. This method eliminates the frequency gaps and reveals interference that may have been missed by the previous EMC testing method. It also identifies each signal and its corresponding magnitude. This test method accurately determines the frequency, amplitude and modulation type at the input to the receiver. With this information, we can determine if significant degradation in the victim receiver will occur, and if so, its extent.

Using a spectrum analyzer, computer and preselector, we successfully completed an investigation at Edwards Air Force Base using this method. We connected the input of the preselector to the VHF antenna coax at the VHF receiver port and monitored the spectrum analyzer. The data gathered enabled us to detect and identify Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) from aircraft avionics. With the information the Air Force was able to make pre-production decisions concerning EMI emission levels.

INTRODUCTION

Interference to antenna-connected onboard intentional emitters (RADARs, EW, etc) is acknowledged by both avionics vendors and the Air Force. It is treated as a special EMC problem area, called RF Compatibility (RFC). RFC includes specialized anechoic chamber and aircraft flight testing for determining interference caused by emitters. However, avionics can be unintentional emitters and can interfere with onboard receivers. The most common source of the interference is harmonics of clock frequencies used in computers and microprocessors. These emission sources have been given little attention from the RFC standpoint. EMC testing in accordance with MIL-E-6051D is generally accomplished by checking discrete radio channels for interference. If all radio channels were tested, which they rarely are, interference could still go undetected if the interfering emissions are below the squelch setting. These undetected emissions can cause severe degradation of the range of the receivers. For example, recognizing the need to maintain a 10 dB signal plus noise to noise ratio (SNR), a signal 1 dB below squelch can cause a factor of ten reduction in range.

In September 1988, we conducted a VHF radio interference test on an aircraft at Edwards Air Force Base. We tested four basic avionics units with emissions exceeding the MIL-STD-461C RE02 limits by connecting an automated Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) receiver to the VHF antenna on the aircraft. The test scanned the FM channels in the 30 MHz to 88 MHz range and the AM channels in the 108 MHz to 156 MHz range.

The effort also included a laboratory test portion which determined the level of interference necessary to cause significant degradation of radio performance. It involved injecting the sum of a modulated intentional signal and an interfering signal into the radio and checking the SNR. We tested the radio with the interfering signal both modulated and unmodulated.

This testing was needed because the vendors of the aforementioned equipment were having severe difficulties in meeting the radiated emission requirements in the VHF frequency range. These vendors were aggressively seeking relaxation of the emission requirements. The extent of the interference to the radio had to be determined

before any relaxation could be considered. The test results showing interference were very useful in motivating the vendors to meet the radiated emission requirements.

BACKGROUND

Many vendors of avionics equipment do not understand the true intent of EMI emissions qualification in accordance with MIL-STD-461/462. The primary purpose of controlling emissions, conducted and radiated, is to prevent these undesired signals from coupling through aircraft antennas to very sensitive tuned receivers. Many avionics suppliers believe that the focus of testing is to prevent these emissions from coupling onto wiring and into other equipment. This incorrect interpretation of the EMI requirements leads to attempts to find a direct relationship between emission and susceptibility levels and to infer a large safety margin between the two levels which can be freely infringed upon whenever necessary. However, there is no intended relationship between these limits. The MIL-STD-461C limits for RS03 and RE02 are graphed together in Figure 1. At 25 MHz, a 116 dB safety margin could be inferred. This would be somewhat justified if the limits were strictly concerned with one-to-one interaction such as wire-to-wire coupling where emissions from one wire might cause a susceptibility condition through coupling to the second wire. Except at power frequencies and for transients, wire-to-wire coupling of "RE02 level" signals is insignificant.

It becomes obvious that a direct relationship between limits is not the intent of the MIL-STDs when you consider aircraft receiver sensitivities below -110 dBm, which drive the emission requirements, and aircraft antenna-connected transmitters with 1000 W (and higher) power outputs, which are the very drivers for many susceptibility requirements. Because of the misconceptions mentioned above, some avionics vendors put little effort into meeting emissions requirements. This attitude has persuaded the Air Force to look for a better way of testing for avionics interference to aircraft receivers.

SELECTION OF TEST EQUIPMENT

In performing this EMC test, our first concern was to determine what sensitivity levels were needed in the test equipment and their frequency accuracy. First we looked at the AN/ARC-164 UHF radio (225-400 MHz, AM) and the AN/ARC-186 VHF radio (30-88 MHz, FM and 108-152 AM). The UHF radio has a closed circuit sensitivity of -101 dBm (2 microvolts into 50 ohms) at a specified SNR of 10 dB with thirty percent AM, 1 KHz. This modulation generates a single spectral line in each sideband which is 16.5 dB less than the carrier. It should be noted that thirty percent AM tone has the same intelligibility as normal.

AM voice (typically greater than eighty percent) and is the criteria used by radio manufacturers. Subtracting the sidelobe level and the SNR requirement from the -101 dBm sensitivity, we obtain a maximum allowable level of -124.5 dBm for any interfering signals. Sensitivity of the VHF AM radio is -103.5 dBm (1.5 microvolts into 50 ohms) which puts the interfering signal level at -127 dBm. For the FM band, the VHF radio has a sensitivity of -117.5 dBm (0.3 microvolts into 50 ohms). An FM analysis requires the interfering signal level to be less than approximately -127 dBm.

We followed the above analysis with laboratory testing of both the UHF and the VHF FM/AM radios to confirm the effects of interference on the radios' performance.

Test results on the receivers are shown in Figures 2 through 4 for SNR versus interfering signal levels. For a 10 dB SNR for the AM receivers, interfering signal levels were 21 dB below the carrier, predicted levels were 23.5 dB. The results for the FM receiver, interfering signal levels were 6 dB below the carrier, with 10 dB levels being predicted by analysis.

In field use of the radios, the typical squelch settings for the UHF, VHF AM and VHF FM are -97.5 dBm (3 microvolts), -103.5 dBm (1.5 microvolts) and -109.5 dBm (0.75 microvolts) respectively. The maximum allowable interfering signal levels related to the squelch settings are -118.5 dBm, -124.5 dBm and -115.5 dBm, respectively. Ideally, the noise floor of the measurement receiver should be several dB below these levels. The noise floor of the spectrum analyzer with preselector available for the test program is between -117 dBm and -127 dBm depending on the selection of receiver bandwidth. Familiarity with the performance criteria and operation of the aircraft and test receivers is essential before planning any test.

The second area of concern is the percentage of frequency uncertainty in the measurement results. Accurately determining interfering signal frequencies is important to minimize the number of radio channels which must be checked during evaluation of performance degradation. During our test at Edwards Air Force Base, we used two percent accuracy uncertainty. For worst case conditions in the UHF band, this selection could result in any undetected interfering signal within one of 160 channels on either side of the channel containing the indicated frequency. Even the use of 0.1 percent accuracy could require tuning of the UHF radio to sixteen channels on either side of the frequency of interest. The other option is to discretely tune the test receiver (spectrum analyzer) using EMI software which allows six digits of accuracy. Either method is acceptable, but discrete tuning will provide a better data base to work with in the future. An additional problem is that the lack of frequency accuracy results in ambiguities in identifying whether a signal originates from

avionics equipment or is due to a previously identified signal present in the ambient environment.

The third area of concern which is not directly related to the test equipment but directly affects the usability of the data collected, is a changing RF environment. If testing is at an open site, ambient measurements should be taken frequently so that there is less ambiguity between signals caused by the ambient and those caused by avionics.

TESTING

The main characteristic of interference signals is that they are primarily generated by harmonics of clocks frequencies used in computers and microprocessors. This source provides a signal at a specific frequency to which a receiver can be tuned and the receiver's AGC can react. These signals are typically Continuous-Wave (CW) or slightly amplitude modulated due to variations in clock current. The results using the AN/ARC-186 and the AN/ARC-164 showed that there is little difference between the effects of either CW or an AM interfering signal as is shown in Figures 5 through 7. As an additional test, we swept the interfering signal across the receiver band while keeping the radio tuned to a single frequency. The responses are shown in Figures 8 through 10. These figures show that as the interfering signal passes through the information bandpass (approximately 150 Hz to 3 KHz on either side of F_c) the SNR is degraded. Once outside the information band the interfering signal has little impact on the SNR.

Testing for interference to radio receivers at the aircraft-level is best accomplished by measuring the noise amplitude on the coaxial cable at the disconnection point to the radio receiver input. This method eliminates antenna gain, antenna pattern, antenna coupler and cable loss calculations or measurements. As with all EMC testing a functional check should be made of every subsystem to be tested to insure they meet basic performance specifications. A signal generator should be used to drive the measurement equipment to confirm that the test set-up is correct. It is also important to verify that the connection is made to the proper antenna, particularly for subsystems with multiple antennas. This concern can be satisfied by driving the coax to the assumed antenna with a signal generator and using a small probe near the antenna to detect the generated field.

Frequency scans should be approximately one third of an octave. Scans should be repeated with all equipment on the aircraft turned off except for the equipment under test. After each scan, the data should be printed and the peaks should be identified using the EMI software. The date and the time should be recorded on each plot, so a complete record is maintained.

If an aircraft test is desired to confirm the interference, several points should be noted. To determine the SNR, a wideband voltmeter will be needed to monitor the audio output. The squelch should be enabled and an intentional signal should be radiated such that it just breaks squelch. This will allow an operational evaluation of the receiver. If the squelch is disabled so that the full receiver sensitivity is reached, a CW signal will have a quieting effect on the radio, thus falsely indicating that no interference is present.

CONCLUSIONS

Test data from the aircraft test at Edwards Air Force Base in September 1988 shows that equipment which does not meet RE02 emissions requirements in the radio band generally causes interference to the receiver. Often the interference is not detected during a radio check but does degrade the operational range of the receiver. This result indicates that the current RE02 limits dictated by MIL-STD-461C are realistic and should be strictly enforced. It is possible that some radio range problems are being caused by RE02 outages that are undetected by the radio checks during standard EMC testing because the interfering signal levels are below the receiver's squelch settings. Consequently, the current EMC radio checks are not adequate for determining EMI in aircraft receivers. Automated measurement of receiver interference should be incorporated into all MIL-E-6051D testing for receiver interference. This type of testing is very useful in motivating equipment vendors to meet the radiated emission requirements of MIL-STD-461C, because it demonstrates their validity.

Frequency accuracy must be maximized in order to prevent uncertainty in the interfering signal's frequency when attempting to distinguish the interference signals from ambient signals and to minimize radio channel selection. Frequent ambient measurements should be made so that the identification of a signal as ambient or interference is easier. Additionally, the ambient in commercial and industrial areas may exceed the required noise levels, thus making it difficult to test for interference. Therefore, a remote site or an anechoic chamber is generally required for testing.

REFERENCE

John C. Zentner, "Aircraft EMC Problems and Their Relationship to Subsystem EMI Requirements", IEEE 1983 National Aerospace and Electronics Conference.

RS03 LIMIT COMPARED TO RE02 LIMIT

FIGURE 1

-103.5 dBm 30% AM SIGNAL (Fc) WITH INTERFERING SIGNAL (Fi) AMPLITUDE REFERENCED TO THE AM SIGNAL

FIGURE 2

-101 dBm 30%, 1kHz AM SIGNAL (Fc) WITH INTERFERENCE SIGNAL (Fi) AMPLITUDE REFERENCED TO THE AM SIGNAL

FIGURE 3

**-109.5 dBm WITH 1kHz MODULATION, 5kHz DEVIATION
WITH INTERFERING SIGNAL AMPLITUDE
REFERENCED TO THE FM SIGNAL**

FIGURE 4

**-103.5 dBm 30% AM SIGNAL (Fc) WITH
AM INTERFERING SIGNAL (Fi) AMPLITUDE
REFERENCED TO THE AM SIGNAL**

FIGURE 5

**-101 dBm 30%, 1kHz AM SIGNAL (Fc) WITH
AM INTERFERENCE SIGNAL (Fi) AMPLITUDE
REFERENCED TO THE AM SIGNAL**

FIGURE 6

**-109.5 dBm FM SIGNAL WITH 1kHz MOD, 5kHz DEVIATION
WITH AN INTERFERING SIGNAL AMPLITUDE
REFERENCED TO THE FM SIGNAL**

FIGURE 7

SIGNAL PLUS NOISE TO NOISE RATIO VERSUS FREQUENCY FOR AN/ARC-186 AM BAND

FIGURE 8

SIGNAL PLUS NOISE TO NOISE RATIO VERSUS FREQUENCY FOR AN/ARC-164

FIGURE 9

SIGNAL PLUS NOISE TO NOISE RATIO VERSUS FREQUENCY CENTERED ABOUT 41 MHz

FIGURE 10